

DIAGNOSIS OF CHANGES IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH VULVOVAGINITIS

Yusufzoda Hosiyat Turon kizi

Resident in the direction of "Medical Radiology"

*Scientific adviser: **Khamidov Obid Abdurakhmonovich**
Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

*Scientific adviser: **Juraev Kamoliddin Danabaevich**
Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Relevance: Infectious diseases of the genital organs are one of the urgent problems of modern gynecology. Vaginal infections cause significant discomfort and negative consequences during pregnancy and childbirth. Although vaginal infections also occur in the hospital, they are often underestimated as a problem in society [3,5,7].

Candidiasis, aerobic vaginitis, bacterial vaginosis are the leading causes of vulvovaginitis, and women have had an episode of infection at least once in their lives, and pregnancy is a predisposing factor for infection of the genital tract [2,6].

Left untreated, these infections can lead to chorioamnionitis followed by spontaneous abortion, preterm birth, premature rupture of membranes, and infection of the fetus or newborn [1,4,8].

Purpose of the study: Data analysis of pregnant women with vulvovaginitis to identify complications and risk factors.

Materials and methods of research: in the maternity complex of the clinic of Samara State Medical University No. 1 for the period 2021-2022, 30 pregnant women with vulvovaginal infections in the third trimester of pregnancy (28-34 weeks) underwent the following examinations: general clinical, laboratory, bacteriological,

bacterioscopic, ultrasound of the uterus and fetal dopplerography, assessment of the birth canal on the Bishop scale.

Research results: The following types of infection were identified in patients: bacterial vaginosis - 12 (40%), vulvovaginal candidiasis - 9 (30%), aerobic vaginitis - 6 (20%), mixed infections - 3 (10%) cases.

As a result of observation, 23 (76.7%) pregnant women had an increased risk of preterm birth and the state of the cervix was assessed using the BISHOP scale. In 2 patients (6.7%), surgical treatment was performed taking into account other indications. In 14 of these pregnancies (46.7%), the pregnancy was maintained after effective treatment.

One patient (3.33%) was diagnosed with chorioamnionitis at 33 weeks of gestation, as a result of which surgery (Caesarean section) was decided by a council of doctors. A male fetus weighing 1800 g was extracted, 3-4 Apgar scores.

Premature rupture of membranes was diagnosed in 21 (70%) cases when patients complained of discharge of water from the vagina in various amounts, 4 of them (19%) had preterm labor.

Polyhydramnios syndrome was detected in 6 (20%) pregnant women during examination, ultrasound diagnosed 10 (33.3%) pregnant women with oligohydramnios. One (3.33%) pregnant woman with a complication of oligohydramnios sought medical help with a diagnosis of an anhydrous gap after 72 hours of observation with a diagnosis of severe malnutrition, an anhydrous gap of the fetus for more than 72 hours was taken for surgical treatment, in patients with pathologies of the amount of water in 11 cases, childbirth were premature. The rest of the pregnant women were under observation and the delivery was urgent.

Conclusions: Thus, it can be concluded that vulvovaginal infection caused by bacterial vaginosis, vulvovaginal candidiasis, aerobic vaginitis and mixed infections complicate the course of pregnancy and childbirth.

In pregnant women with vulvovaginitis, preterm birth was in 26.7%, chorioamnionitis in 3.3%, intrauterine rupture of membranes was in 70%, oligohydramnios in 33.3% and polyhydramnios in 20%.

References:

1. Александрова В. В. Этиологическая структура кандидозных вульвовагинитов у беременных //Forcipe. – 2019. – №. Приложение.
2. Ахтамова Н. А. и др. Инновационный метод лечения хронической тазовой боли //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 12 (53). – С. 89-91.
3. Ахтамова Н. А., Наргиз Ш., Тияльова С. А. ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ МЕТОД ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ТАЗОВОЙ БОЛИ //Re-health journal. – 2021. – №. 1 (9).
4. Амирзода Т. С., ШОПУЛОТОВ Ш. А. НЕДЕРЖАНИЕ МОЧИ И НЕУДЕРЖАНИЕ МОЧИ: КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ //ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 5.
5. Закирова, Н., Туракулова, Ш., Эшматов, С., Хасанова, Д., Курбаниязова, В., & Нуридинова, Ш. (2017). Акушерские и перинатальные исходы беременности при артериальной гипотензии. Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины, (1 (93), 195–197.
6. Курбаниязов З. Б. и др. Хирургическое лечение больных с синдромом Мириizzi //Врач-аспирант. – 2012. – Т. 51. – №. 2.1. – С. 135-138.
7. АмировнаТИЛЯВОВА С., ХУДОЯРОВА Д. Р. РЕАЛИИ ВРЕМЕНИ. СИНДРОМ ГИПЕРАКТИВНОГО МОЧЕВОГО ПУЗЫРЯ И ПРЕМЕНОПАУЗА //БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ. – С. 25.
8. Тютюнник В. Л., Кан Н. Е., Ломова Н. А. Современные аспекты терапии неспецифического вульвовагинита при беременности //Медицинский совет. – 2018. – №. 7. – С. 102-105.

9. Тоджиева Н., Курбаниязова В. Эффективность применения пролонгированного режима комбинированных оральных контрацептивов при лечении гиперпластических процессов эндометрия //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2016. – №. 4 (91). – С. 93-96.
10. РИЗАЕВ Ж. А., АХРОРОВА М. Ш. Оценка особенностей изменения слизистой оболочки и состояния полости рта при covid-19 //Журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 4.
11. Рустамова Ш. Б., Худоярова Д. Р., Элтазарова Г. Ш. Особенности течения беременности и исход родов на фоне цервицита шейки матки //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 13 (54). – С. 70-72.
12. Худоярова Д. Р., Кобилова З. А., Шопулотов Ш. А. Возможности инновационного метода обучения–геймификация //Онтологические и социокультурные основания альтернативного проекта глобализации.— Екатеринбург, 2021. – 2021. – С. 361-364.
13. Худоярова Д. Р., Шавкатова Г. Ш. ЭНДОМЕТРИЙ ПОЛИПЛАРИНИ ТАШХИСЛАШ ВА ДАВОЛАШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.
14. Шавкатова Г. Ш., Худоярова Д. Р., Абдуллаева Н. Н. МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКИЙ СИНДРОМ И НОВЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЕГО КОРРЕКЦИИ
15. Askarova F. K., Yakhshinorov I. N. Risk Factors and Recommendations for the Treatment of Anemia in Pregnant Women (Literature Review) //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 190-193.
16. Askarova F. K. The Negative Impact of Vitamin D and Other Micronutrient Deficiencies in Pregnant Women //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 380-382.
17. ISKANDAROVNA T. N., RAKHIMOVNA K. D. RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES IN PREMENOPAUSE //БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ. – С. 72.

18. Tilyavova S. A., Karimova G. S. Realities Of Time. Chronic Gender Inflammation And Pelvic Pain //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 03. – C. 2020.
19. Todjiyeva N., Vohidov S., Rajabov A. ENDOMETRIUM AND ITS HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 355-359.
20. Shavkatova G. S., Xudoyarova D. R., Shopulotova Z. A. Metabolik sindrom-zamonaviy jamiyatning muammosi //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 486-491.
21. Shavkatovna S. G., Rakhimovna K. D., Khudoyarova D. R. STUDY AND TREATMENT OF THE ORIGINS OF OBESITY IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Next Scientists Conferences. – 2022. – C. 46-51.

